

KGI4NFDI

Knowledge Graph Infrastructure for the German National Research Data Infrastructure

Services for creating, discovering, connecting, and using knowledge graphs for NFDI,
EOSC and beyond

Proposal for the Integration phase of a Basic Service in Base4NFDI

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1 General Information

- **Name of proposed Basic Service:** (in English):
Knowledge Graph Infrastructure for the German National Research Data Infrastructure
- **Acronym of the proposed Basic Service:** KGI4NFDI
- **Service "subtitle" explaining key functionality:**
Services for creating, discovering, connecting, and using knowledge graphs for NFDI,

EOSC and beyond

- **Corresponding NFDI Section:** (Meta)data, Terminologies, Provenance
- **Lead institution:** ZB MED – Information Centre for Life Sciences, Gleueler Strasse 60, 50931 Cologne
- **Name of lead institution principal investigator:** Prof. Dr. Konrad Förstner, foerstner@zbmed.de
- **Participating institutions:**

Principal Investigator	Institution, location	Contact E-mail	Member in [consortium] ¹	Funding requested [yes no]
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Table 1: List of participating institutions

- **Initialisation Phase:** June 2024 - May 2025
- **Planned duration of the integration phase:** Two years
- **Statement on efforts required by consortia for integration of service**

¹ Name one DFG consortium the institution is or has a route to become a member of and through which funds should be appropriated if this proposal is approved.

KGI4NFDI aims to make the use, deployment, and maintenance of Knowledge Graphs (KGs) simple and scalable. The effort needed from consortia is flexible and tailored to their specific needs, ranging from minimal to more involved activities. Through structured incubator calls and consultancy office hours, we make deploying and configuring KGs a smooth and well-supported process. Depending on the starting point, targeted simple steps guide consortia to configure and contribute new or existing KGs to the central Hub and Registry and thereby unlock multiple advantages of cross-institutional and cross-disciplinary interoperability and seamless connection to global resources (including OpenAIRE, Wikidata, EOSC and more).

- **Summary of the proposal in English and German**

The KGI4NFDI aims to support the creation, discovery, connection, and use of KGs within the NFDI ecosystem, EOSC, and beyond. This Basic Service builds upon the achievements of the Initialisation Phase and addresses the increasing demand for KG deployment, a central KG Hub, interoperability, and community engagement. In this context, an incubator program will enable projects to generate and maintain KGs supported by KGI4NFDI, facilitating decentralised KG instances based on standards and tried-and-tested approaches. Furthermore, Registry and Hub services are refined to provide a more user-friendly interface for querying across different KGs with improved semantic interoperability. Consultancy services will be expanded to actively engage the NFDI community in the creation and use of KGs through various initiatives, including workshops, webinars, and dedicated events. Our approach is expected to contribute significantly to the vision of “One NFDI” by promoting the standardisation practices that enhance data integration capabilities. We also align with prevalent international initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), creating a sustainable KG infrastructure. Feedback from the Initialisation phase offered valuable insights from the NFDI community, some aligning with the Initialisation phase's scope and others thoughtfully incorporated into the proposal for the Integration phase.

Ziel von KGI4NFDI ist es, die Erstellung, Entdeckung, Verbindung und Nutzung von Wissensgraphen (Knowledge Graphs, KG) innerhalb des NFDI-Ökosystems, der EOSC und darüber hinaus zu unterstützen. Dieser Basisdienst baut auf den Resultaten der Initialisierungsphase auf und adressiert die steigende Nachfrage nach Bereitstellung von KGs, einem zentralen KG-Hub, Interoperabilität und dem Einbinden der Community. In einem Inkubatorprogramm werden Projekte in die Lage versetzt, KGs zu erstellen und zu pflegen, um dezentrale KG-Instanzen auf Basis von Standards und bewährten Ansätzen zu ermöglichen. Darüber hinaus werden Registry- und Hub-Dienste verfeinert, um eine benutzerfreundliche Schnittstelle für die Abfrage verschiedener KGs mit semantischer Interoperabilität zu schaffen. Die Beratungsdienste werden ausgeweitet, um die NFDI-Gemeinschaft durch Aktivitäten wie Workshops, Webinare und spezielle Veranstaltungen in die Erstellung und Nutzung von KGs einzubinden. Es wird erwartet, dass unser Ansatz durch die Förderung von Standards, die die

Datenintegration verbessern, einen wichtigen Beitrag zur Vision der „One NFDI“ leistet. Wir sind auch im Austausch mit internationalen Initiativen wie der European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) und schaffen eine nachhaltige KG-Infrastruktur. Feedback aus der Initialisierungsphase lieferte wertvolle Erkenntnisse, von denen einige direkt adressiert und andere in den Antrag für die Integrationsphase aufgenommen wurden.

2 Summary of Initialisation Phase Results

2.1 Change in Background and Motivation since the start of the Initialisation Phase

There are no changes in motivation and background since the start of the Initialisation Phase.

2.2 Results of the Initialisation Phase

In the initial seven months since its inception, the KGI4NFDI project has achieved significant results. A central Hub and Registry have been set up to aggregate information on KGs contributed by NFDI consortia and research communities. A comprehensive survey was conducted to refine and optimize the KGI services. Consultancy services were established to support consortium members in creating their own KG solutions. [Guidelines](#) for creating, hosting, and using KGs were compiled and [open-sourced](#). The monthly consultancy hours started on 15.01.2025. The consultancy requests are received via the KGI4NFDI mailing list and documented. In addition, a range of queries has been explored as the basis for showcases. A harmonisation strategy has also been developed to ensure consistency across different consortia's ontologies. These accomplishments demonstrate the project's potential for fostering standardisation of ontological practices and enhancing data integration capabilities. Also the questions of the need of KGs in NFDI raised by the Technical Expert Committee (TEC) has been answered as several consortia and institutions have reported their interest and are in exchange with the KGI4NFDI project team to initiate the creation of KGs. The survey results also clearly document the need.

Registry and Hub: Information about KGs maintained by the consortia was compiled and modelled using two alternating ontologies, DCAT and NFDIcore. Subsequently, triplet datasets (KG registry) were generated. We host the KG engines and SPARQL endpoints that serve the generated datasets. Two engines were tested for this, Apache Fuseki and QLever, after which QLever was selected for its superior performance. A web interface for the SPARQL endpoint was developed to serve the KG Registry dataset and was published under subdomains^{2 3} of

² <https://kgi.services.base4nfdi.de>

³ <https://sparql.kgi.services.base4nfdi.de>

Base4NFDI. Additionally, a web portal was developed as the landing page for KGI4NFDI. All development code is maintained in GitHub repositories^{4 5}, incorporating a CI/CD pipeline for automated deployment. Containerization using Docker is used to streamline deployment and ensure environmental consistency across different development stages. The Hub will be further developed as suggested by the TEC to offer overarching query solutions, making it one joint resource for all disciplines.

Consultancy: The guidelines for creating, using, and querying KGs were compiled and released under open CC-BY license at GitHub⁶. The guidelines, deployed at GitHub Pages⁷, are openly accessible. The resources cover installation and configuration, data import and modelling, and querying the KGs using Apache Jena (Fuseki), Virtuoso, Wikibase, and QLever. Additionally, the consultancy sessions have started via e-mails in December 2024 and via Zoom on 15.01.2025. The consultancy requests and sessions are documented in Google Drive and showed that NFDI communities need a service for outsourcing the deployment of KGs.

Interoperability Strategy: For the interoperability strategy, investigations on existing frameworks and initiatives as well as a stakeholder analysis have been conducted. As a result, interoperability dimensions specifically for the use cases of KG generation and KG access have been defined. Moreover, best practices and guidelines to facilitate metadata mapping, linking, and integration are currently under development and will be published as part of the KGI4NFDI Guidelines. Example queries for single KGs, but also for conducting federated queries are being developed. They will be part of the Registry and aim to facilitate access and insight of the registered KGs.

2.2.1 Interim report on requirements for finalisation of the initialisation phase

a) Requirements analysis (D1.4.1)

Due: 3 months after start date | Percent finished 90% | Status: **running**

Overview of relevant outcomes: We have gathered feedback on different aspects of KG adoption and use across NFDI consortia, including potential support that KGI4NFDI could provide.

Deliverables and Milestones: Interviews with NFDI Consortias (reported in D1.4.1 Requirements analysis), D4.1 Survey of existing KG adoption practices in NFDI.

Outlook: We are currently preparing the survey analysis for publishing and scheduling follow-up interviews with survey participants that expressed such a need.

⁴ <https://github.com/base4nfdi/kgi4nfdi/>

⁵ <https://github.com/KGI4NFDI>

⁶ <https://github.com/KGI4NFDI/Guidelines>

⁷ <https://kgi4nfdi.github.io/Guidelines>

b) Software evaluation (D1.4.2)

Due: 6 months after start date | Percent finished 100% | Status: **finished**

Overview of relevant outcomes: prioritization of NFDICore over DCAT (better aligning attributes, part of NFDI ecosystem), prioritization of Qlever over Apache Jena and Wikibase (Qlever has better performance, YasGUI is selected as a user-friendly query service).

Deliverables and Milestones: D1.1 Registry of KGs in NFDI, D1.2 Platform for search and query across KGs.

Outlook: Performance, functionality, and usability will be further monitored.

c) Service design (D1.4.3)

Due: 6 months after start date | Percent finished 90% | Status: **running**

Overview of relevant outcomes: The design for the KG Registry and the query service have been finalized and documented.

Deliverables and Milestones: D1.1 Registry of KGs in NFDI, D1.2 Platform for search and query across KGs, Task: Documentation template setup, Task: Create KG submission form on GitHub, specification of interoperability dimensions.

Outlook: Metadata model for KG submission form needs to be finalized.

d) Service prototype (D1.4.4)

Due: 12 months after start date | Percent finished 70% | Status: **running**

Overview of relevant outcomes: Registry of KG prototype implemented; Consultancy service is running regularly; Report comprising analysis of existing interoperability frameworks, specified interoperability dimensions, and best practices; Guidelines for metadata mapping, linking, integration; Report on engagement towards interoperability issues with national and international initiatives.

Deliverables and Milestones: D1.1 Registry of KGs in NFDI, D1.2 Platform for search and query across KGs, D2.2 Consultancy service, D3.1 Strategy for metadata mapping, linking, and integration, D3.2 Strategy for interoperability with national and international KG initiatives, D4.2 Showcases.

Outlook: Reports on interoperability will be finalized. Search functionality will be implemented on the KG Registry. Showcases will be integrated with the Registry and Hub and aligned with the strategies for metadata mapping and interoperability.

e) Service piloting and user testing (D1.4.5)

Due: 12 months after start date | Percent finished 70% | Status: **running**

Overview of relevant outcomes: Registry of KGs in NFDI is openly deployed and tested by partner institutions. Guidelines for creating and hosting KGs using four KG-software (Wikibase, Apache Jena, Virtuoso, and QLever) are compiled, open-sourced at GitHub, and openly deployed at GitHub Pages. Users can provide their feedback via GitHub issues.

Deliverables and Milestones: D1.1 Registry of KGs in NFDI, D1.2 Platform for search and query across KGs, D2.1 Guidelines for creating and hosting KGs, M2.1 Guidelines available online, Task: Wikibase deployment guidelines, Task: Apache Jena deployment guidelines, Task: Virtuoso deployment guidelines, Task: QLever deployment guidelines.

Outlook: KG Registry and Platform for search and query will be advertised publicly and user feedback will be collected.

2.2.2 Other

Creation of five User Personas with multiple User Stories during multiple workshops. Participation at Base4NFDI User conference, Base4NFDI Services Roadshow, and EOSC Symposium 2024.

2.3 Update on Technical Readiness Level (TRL) of the Basic Service

While the TLR of the underlying open-source software is high (8 - 9), the Registry and Hub are still under development, providing a TRL of 6.

3 Working Concept for the development of the Basic Service

The KGI4NFDI is designed to support creating, managing, using, discovering, and querying KGs within the NFDI ecosystem. This Basic Service builds upon the outcomes of the Initialization Phase and addresses the growing need for deployment of KGs, semantic interoperability, and community engagement. The integration phase will solidify the foundational components of KGI4NFDI while scaling its services to a broader audience. The development of the Basic Service is structured to balance technical advancements with community engagement. The focus is on achieving interoperability across technical, semantic, and organizational levels while fostering collaboration among NFDI consortia, research institutions, and international initiatives. By aligning with standards like the NFDIcore Ontology, KGI4NFDI aims to simplify KG adoption, enhance discoverability, and promote cross-disciplinary research. During the integration phase, KGI4NFDI will provide consultancy, training, and open educational resources, engaging with the NFDI 'Knowledge Graphs' group and initiatives like EOSC to ensure global alignment and interoperability. With a clear focus on scalability, sustainability, and openness, the integration phase sets the stage for transitioning KGI4NFDI into the Ramping Up phase, where it will achieve its full potential as a central resource for the NFDI community and beyond.

3.1 Service Integration Concept

The integration of KGI4NFDI services with partner consortia will aim for technical, semantic, and organizational interoperability across the NFDI landscape. This approach ensures that KGI4NFDI serves as a unifying infrastructure, enhancing the usability and accessibility of KGs within and beyond the NFDI community. KGI4NFDI will integrate KGs from partner consortia (including but not limited to MaRDI, NFDI4Culture, and NFDI4Microbiota) into its central KG Hub. This integration will allow for efficient querying and retrieval of metadata across consortia following the established interoperability standards. The NFDIcore Ontology⁸ will be adopted as the semantic framework for integration, ensuring consistency and alignment across diverse KGs. Collaboration with Base Services, such as IAM4NFDI and TS4NFDI, will further enhance interoperability and cumulatively strengthen the value proposition of all services to their respective users, and future integrations are planned under WP5 to include more Base Services as they become available. On an organizational level, all project partners are active members of various NFDI consortia, ensuring that the integration strategy is aligned with the broader goals of the NFDI community. Regular collaboration through workshops, working group meetings (e.g., the NFDI working group "Knowledge Graphs" in Section Metadata), and project-specific engagements will strengthen these ties and foster a shared vision for KG adoption. Services developed within individual consortia that are relevant to this vision, e.g. Wikibase4Research⁹ and the NFDIcore Ontology, originally developed in the context of NFDI4Culture, will be tightly integrated in the architecture and service offerings of KGI. Additionally, to support partner consortia, KGI4NFDI will offer consultancy services and training sessions through WP4. Workshops and knowledge-sharing events, such as the NFDI Knowledge Graph Day and webinars, will promote the adoption of standards and demonstrate the benefits of interoperable KGs. Feedback mechanisms, including surveys and consultation sessions, will ensure continuous improvement and alignment with user needs.

The success of the integration phase will be measured using a set of key performance indicators (KPIs). Technical KPIs will include the number of integrated KGs, compliance with the NFDIcore Ontology, system uptime, and query response times. Community KPIs will focus on the number of workshops conducted, participants engaged, and consultancy requests resolved. Adoption KPIs will measure the number of consortia and institutions contributing to the central Hub and Registry. KGI4NFDI remains committed to openness, with all software components using open licenses and outputs such as documentation, training materials, and datasets being openly accessible. Proprietary software or components will only be considered if justified by technical or operational

⁸ <https://ise-fizkarlsruhe.github.io/nfdicore/>

⁹ <https://gitlab.com/nfdi4culture/wikibase4research>

needs. KGI4NFDI complements existing **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Node** offerings by focusing on KGs as a foundational technology. Integration with EOSC standards and services will promote the reuse of KG data and align KGI4NFDI as a **valuable EOSC Node resource**. Additionally, collaboration with EOSC will enhance international interoperability and contribute to the global research data ecosystem. These efforts build on WP2 results - harmonized ontologies, benchmark queries, and a query gallery - ensuring semantic alignment and technical consistency for integrating KGs across consortia and the EOSC framework.

3.2 Future Development and Ramp-up Outlook

The plan for the integration phase is to reach a service that fulfills the requirements for the ramping up phase. This includes that we aim to reach a TRL of 7-8 which is based on a state-of-the-art technology stack that enables us to reach TRL 9 eventually. Apart from the technical development, this requires also a concept for sustainable operation of the service. Here, we aim to build on the proposed NFDI Multi Cloud Service¹⁰ and will collaborate closely with the working group or base service (see also WP5). With our incubator activities, we plan to not only increase but also to strengthen our collaborations with other NFDI consortia (see WP3). With a special focus on KGs, we complement existing EOSC EU node services. After presenting KGI4NFDI at the EOSC Symposium 2024, we plan to continue and increase our engagement on EU level.

3.3 Risks and Challenges

Several potential risks were identified and measures to mitigate them planned: **A) Lack of Adoption by the NFDI Community:** There is a potential risk that the proposed Knowledge Graph Infrastructure (KGI) and its components may not gain sufficient traction or adoption among the NFDI community. To proactively address this risk, the project will involve active engagement with various NFDI consortia during the planning and implementation phases. This will include 1) **Consultations and discussions** with consortia to gather insights, address concerns, and align the infrastructure with community needs. 2) **Letters of Commitment (LoCs)** from participating consortia to confirm their intention to actively engage with the incubator program and adopt the proposed KGI solutions. 3) Tailored **workshops and webinars** to introduce the infrastructure, train users, and demonstrate its value, ensuring a smooth onboarding process for the community. **B) Parallel Development with similar Initiatives:** Overlaps or duplication of efforts with parallel initiatives, such as OpenAIRE or other international projects, may result in resource inefficiencies and fragmentation of efforts. To mitigate this risk, the project will prioritize collaboration and open communication with similar initiatives, including: 1) Establishing **formal exchanges and**

¹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/6510971>

coordination mechanisms with OpenAIRE to identify synergies, reduce redundancies, and align objectives. 2) Participating in **international working groups and forums** related to KG development and semantic interoperability.

4 Support Actions from Base4NFDI / NFDI Sections, and Integrating NFDI Consortia / Efforts

Support from	Work package / Description of contribution	Contact person Basic Service
Base4NFDI; Section Common Infra.; Section Metadata	WP 1 “Hub and Registry” Support coordination with related Base Services, such as IAM4NFDI, TS4NFDI, PID4NFDI, etc.j	B. Zapilko, K. Förstner
Base4NFDI; Section Common Infra.; Section Metadata - WG “Ontology mapping and harmonization”	WP 2 “Interoperability” : Support interoperability and alignment with related Base Services and individual NFDI consortia, as well as relevant initiatives outside the NFDI.	D. Mietchen, F. Limani
Base4NFDI; Section Common Infra.; Section Metadata; KGI4NFDI Partner institutions	WP 3 “Incubators and Deployment” : Provide a broader outreach to the interested NFDI consortia in adopting and/or extending the practices and services being developed in the KGI4NFDI. This also includes organizations that are not (yet) part of the NFDI.	F. Limani, R. Shigapov
Base4NFDI; Section Metadata - WG “Knowledge Graphs”	WP 4 “Community Engagement and Consultancy” : Support in promoting the role of and adoption of KGs and corresponding practices.	R. Shigapov, L. Rossenova
Base4NFDI; Section Metadata - WG “Knowledge Graphs”	WP 5 “Integration and collaboration with other Base Services” : Support the integration of Base services currently in their integration phase.	L. Rossenova, D. Mietchen

Table 2: Support needed from Base4NFDI / Service Stewards / Section

5 Work Programme

The following working programme was also developed based on the experiences and the feedback gathered from our community survey conducted from December 5, 2024, to December 31, 2024¹¹ as well in close exchange with the Base4NFDI team and other Base4NFDI services, especially TS4NFDI.

Figure 1: Overview of the KGI4NFDI working programme in the Integration Phase.

5.1 Overview of Work Packages

Work package	Deliverables (D) and milestones (M)	Responsible partner(s)
1. Hub and Registry	D1.1: Advanced version of the Hub (Q3) D1.2: Advanced version of the Registry (Q6) D1.3: Testing suite (Q7) D1.4: User study of Registry and Hub (Q8) M1.1: Central Knowledge Management Infrastructure for KGI4NFDI (Q8)	GESIS (contributions: TIB, ZB MED)
2. Interoperability	D2.1: Definition of benchmark queries for assessing KG interoperability (Q1) D2.2: Ontology and License fields available in the Hub (Q3) D2.3: Final report on EOSCxNFDI KG interoperability published (Q7) M2.1: Semantic Interoperability KPIs defined (Q2) M2.2: Gallery of actionable queries accessible (Q4) M2.3: First evaluation of interoperability measures released (Q6) M2.4: Collection of EOSCxNFDI success stories released (Q8)	FIZ (contributions: ZBW)
3. Incubators and Deployment	D3.1: Publish incubator project guideline (Q1) D3.2: Deployment pipelines are tested for both scenarios (Q3) D3.3: Deployment documentation is published online (Q4) D3.4: Publish a report for each incubator cycle (Q7) D3.5: Publish an overall report on the incubation outcome and best practices (Q8) M3.1: The first incubator cycle completes (Q4) M3.2: The second incubator cycle completes (Q5)	ZBW (contributions: UB Mannheim)

¹¹ Report: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14717742>

	M3.3: The third incubator cycle completes (Q6) M3.4: The fourth incubator cycle completes (Q8)	
4. Community Engagement and Consultancy	D4.1: Strategy for Community Engagement and Consultancy (Q1) D4.2: Open educational resources are compiled (Q4) D4.3: Knowledge graph events are organised (Q5 with extensions to Q8) D4.4: Community impact report (Q8) M4.1: Launch of Community Engagement activities (Q2) M4.2: Evaluation and reporting (Q8)	UB Mannheim (contribution: TIB, ZBW)
5. Integration and collaboration with other Base Services	D5.1: Report on integration results, use cases and best practices (Q8) M5.1: Integration with services currently in their integration phase (Q2) M5.2: Integration with services currently in their initialisation phase (Q5) M5.3: Integration with upcoming services (Q7)	TIB (contribution: FIZ, ZB MED)
6. Coordination and Outreach	D6.1: Kick-off meeting for the Integration phase (Q1) D6.2: Definition of KPIs (Q2) D6.3: Outreach strategy (Q3) D6.4: Midterm-Report (Q4) D6.5: Ramping up phase proposal (Q7) D6.6: Final report (Q8) M6.1: KPIs defined and collection implemented (Q2) M6.2: Submission of the Ramping Up Phase proposal (Q7) M6.2: Project phase conclusion (Q8)	ZB MED (contribution: all)

Table 4: Overall work programme with work packages, deliverables, milestones, and responsible partner

5.2 Detailed Work Programme

Work Packages, Tasks, Deliverables and Milestones	Base Service “Knowledge Graph Infrastructure”							
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8
WP1: Hub and Registry								
Deliverables			D1.1			D1.2	D1.3	D1.4
Milestones								M1.1
WP2: Interoperability								
Deliverables	D2.1		D2.2				D2.3	
Milestones		M2.1		M2.2		M2.3		M2.4
WP3: Incubators & Deployment								
Deliverables	D3.1		D3.2	D3.3			D3.4	D3.5
Milestones				M3.1	M3.2	M3.3		M3.4
WP4: Community engagement and consultancy								
Deliverables	D4.1			D4.2	D4.3			D4.4
Milestones		M4.1						M4.2
WP5: Integration and collaboration with other Base Services								
Deliverables								D5.1
Milestones		M5.1			M5.2		M5.3	
WP6: Coordination and Outreach								
Deliverables	D6.1	D6.2	D6.3	D6.4			D6.5	D6.6
Milestones		M6.1					M6.2	M6.3

Chart 1: Gantt chart with work packages (WPx), deliverables (Dx.y), and milestones (Mx.y).

5.2.1 WP1 - Hub and Registry

The “Hub and Registry” Working Package aims to establish a central knowledge management infrastructure for the KGI4NFDI service, with two key components: the Hub and the Registry. The Registry, initiated during the Initialisation Phase, will be extended by incorporating new KGs registered by NFDI consortia or generated during the incubator projects. Reusing the NFDIcore Ontology for representing the KGs within the Registry ensures interoperability, providing a robust foundation for knowledge sharing and discovery across the KGI4NFDI ecosystem. The Hub, initially built during the Initialisation Phase, will be extended to provide a centralized access point for querying and retrieving information across different KGs registered in the Registry. To facilitate access, the Hub will provide several example queries within single KGs as well as across multiple KGs. Both Hub and Registry will be further developed to shift them from a prototypical stage to a production system with a higher TRL. This includes the integration of standard software testing routines like unit testing, integration testing as well as functional tests and user tests with external users. Results from user tests can be considered for further improvement of Hub and Registry. Furthermore, we will explore the possibilities of a natural language interface for querying KGs based on open Large Language Models (LLMs).

5.2.2 WP2 - Interoperability

The Interoperability Working Package is aimed at ensuring seamless interoperability - with an **initial focus on semantic interoperability** - at **two main levels**: between NFDI-related KGs (**NFDI level**) as well as between KGI4NFDI and other relevant initiatives and resources, both within and beyond NFDI (**EOSC level**) and internationally. Alignment with Semantic Web standards, relevant Basic Services and related protocols is crucial for both levels, as is legal and policy interoperability, particularly concerning licensing and data protection. In addition, semantic interoperability for the NFDI level rests on **alignment and normalisation of data models** between and across NFDI KGs and associated tooling, particularly for data validation and integration. These data models include notions of alignment with pertinent ontologies and attention to data types, data formats, value normalisation, consistency checks and community-specific adaptations. Relevant **tooling** includes provisions for querying KGs as well as other basic functionalities like import (e.g. from non-KG data sources), export (e.g. as subgraphs), format conversions (e.g. to and from nanopublications), quality checks (e.g. schema compliance) or visualisations (e.g. for research or education). These technical measures will be combined with a harmonised approach to describing NFDI-related KGs and documenting their creation and use. Building on existing collaborations with national and international partners, these NFDI level interoperability efforts will be synchronised with infrastructure providers at the EOSC level and beyond, which requires exploring, documenting

and handling additional technical and policy parameters. These partnering infrastructure providers include Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC), OpenAIRE and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), the Wikimedia Foundation and providers of research KGs more generally.

5.2.3 WP3 - Incubators and Deployment

This Work Package is designed to provide a structured pathway for interested communities to adopt or expand KG practices in alignment with the KGI4NFDI deliverables. It also aims to encourage exploration of new aspects, such as emerging technologies, innovative use cases, and illustrative showcases. Building on the successful experiences of other Base4NFDI services like IAM4NFDI and TS4NFDI, this Work Package will launch a Call for Incubator Projects. These calls will invite proposals from NFDI consortia or research communities interested in leveraging KGI-based services.

Figure 2: Workflow of the Incubator calls.

The incubator approach involves projects working through a series of focused sprints, with each incubator cycle lasting approximately six months. Working through the sprints, participants are expected to deliver a functional KG at the end of the cycle. Proposals submitted in response to the incubator calls will be evaluated by the Main Incubator Board. This board comprises experts in KG development, research infrastructure, and NFDI-related topics, ensuring thorough and informed review processes. We aim to select a maximum of 10 projects, which should foster collaboration and KG development within the NFDI community. Incubators will also be implemented in close collaboration with related Base4NFDI project, especially the TS4NFDI. KG deployment is the other component of this WP: not all communities have the necessary (deployment) infrastructure to put their KGs in production, and this component will enable the incubation cycle to generate a Minimum Viable Product (MVP). We plan for a multicloud deployment strategy (see WP5) to cater to a broader set of requirements. If a multicloud service is not available, the alternative is to work with the partners towards a suitable solution.

5.2.4 WP4 - Community engagement and consultancy

This work package will engage the NFDI community, offering consultancy and support for adopting and integrating KGs into research workflows. Serving as a central contact point, WP4 aims to establish KGs as a key technology for semantic data integration and improved data management. Activities will focus on collaboration, knowledge-sharing, and capacity building. Our **consultancy services** will offer one-on-one or small-group sessions to address specific challenges faced by researchers, consortia, or institutions in their KG projects. The **workshops and training sessions** will be designed and organised to build practical skills for using KGs. **Open educational resources** on KGs will be compiled to ensure sustainability of KG practices. The WP4 will organise the knowledge-sharing events such as the **NFDI Knowledge Graph Day, webinars, and panel discussions** to share KG use cases and stimulate cross-disciplinary collaboration. Engagement with the NFDI working group "Knowledge Graphs" in Section Metadata will continue through regular meetings to discuss advancements, challenges, and opportunities in the field. WP4 will also integrate **feedback mechanisms** to ensure continuous improvement, including post-event surveys and an online feedback form. WP4 will measure its success through defined KPIs, such as the number of workshops conducted, participants engaged, consultancy requests resolved, and the number of educational resources compiled. By implementing these activities, WP4 aims to establish an engaged community around KGs, enhance research and research data management practices through usage of KGs, and position KGs as a key technology within the NFDI ecosystem.

5.2.5 WP5 - Integration and collaboration with other Base Services

This work package will focus on enabling technical integration and collaboration with existing Base Services that can be used within the KGI service or alternatively, that can make use of the KGI service. The work will be split into three phases resulting in three milestones and one key reporting deliverable. In the first phase of the work we will engage with services that are more developed and can already be integrated on a technical level. We envision tight coordination with the **TS4NFDI** service. Embedding access to TS widgets in the service Hub and Registry will facilitate better data integration as well as easier querying. Additionally, support for the **IAM4NFDI** service will enable personalization features in the Hub, such as saving queries for example, which will be easily accessible to anyone with an existing NFDI account login. In the second phase of the work we will consider services that are still being actively developed, but offer various routes for integration and closer cooperation. We plan to coordinate with the **Jupyter4NFDI** service in integrating Jupyter notebooks to query (the Hub) and/or deploy individual KGs. With the **RDMTraining4NFDI** services, we can benefit from shared materials regarding the use, querying and deployment of KGs. **software.NFDI** and **DMP4NFDI** service provide further resources for the

users of our service to refer to when it comes to selecting software tooling and managing data to be stored in a KG, which can be integrated in our Consulting and Deployment activities (**WP4**). In the third phase of the work we will consider new and upcoming services. One of the services where we foresee direct integration potential is the **MC4NFDI** project offering cloud infrastructure for service deployment. This would be a valuable resource to our service users which could help automate and distribute the technical complexity of deploying and hosting your own KG. Since many of our consultancy requests we have received to date were focused on help not only with the management of data in KGs but also with the running and hosting of individual instances, we believe this would be a valuable collaboration opportunity between two base services. Alternatively, we will have to look for other hosting infrastructure solutions in our Ramping Up phase. Furthermore, through active outreach activities (**WP6**), we hope to explore potential synergies with other upcoming services and incubator opportunities that are yet to be announced. At the Integration Phase's conclusion, we will publish a technical report detailing use cases, best practices, and links to code repositories for service integrations.

5.2.6 WP6 - Coordination and Outreach

The Coordination and Outreach Working Package will facilitate seamless collaboration among the six funded partners throughout the Integration Phase. This will be achieved by organizing regular project meetings with a defined agenda covering progress updates, discussion of key issues, and decision-making. A **Scientific Advisory Board** will be established and meet twice a year in a virtual format to review project progress, address strategic issues, and make high-level decisions. The working package will keep in close exchange with the BASE4NFDI team and engage with other relevant stakeholders, such as other NFDI consortia, relevant research communities and other KG providers (e.g. OpenAIRE and HMC). Project progress will be monitored by tracking key KPIs to assess project effectiveness and identify areas for improvement. In terms of outreach, the working package will focus on raising awareness of the KGI4NFDI project and its outcomes within NFDI contexts as well as the broader research community also on an international level. This will involve developing and implementing a comprehensive outreach strategy, creating engaging **communication materials** (together with WP4) and utilizing appropriate communication channels to reach target audiences, including scientific conferences, workshops, online platforms, and social media. This work package will **organize public events** like workshops, seminars, and webinars to share project progress and results, while engaging with the research community through conferences and exhibitions. Dissemination efforts include publishing findings in peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings, making data and resources openly accessible, and preparing reports and presentations for stakeholders and the public. Additionally, it will coordinate the follow-up proposal for the project's Ramping up phase.